

1 **An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: Lrrc37a3.**

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6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with
7 trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to
8 HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of Lrrc37a3 as a
9 candidate gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

10 Citations

11 1. Libe-Philippot, B., Lejeune, A., Wierda, K., Louros, N., Erkol, E., Vlaeminck, I., Beckers, S.,
12 Gaspariunaite, V., Bilheu, A., Konstantoulea, K. and Nyitrai, H., 2023. LRRC37B is a human modifier of
13 voltage-gated sodium channels and axon excitability in cortical neurons. Cell, 186(26), pp.5766-5783.